

Assessing the Impact of VIRTUAL CLASSROOMS via Student and Teacher Feedback

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Abstract

Virtual Classrooms were expected to be more effective than the traditional classrooms, especially during the Covid when this format of education was the only way to continue the learning process. Both teachers and students faced challenges, but they also observed some improvements in their punctuality and got a better understanding of this format in the future. We conducted interviews and surveys among university teachers and students in Astana. In total, we had 22 respondents to our survey and 3 students participated in our interview. The violation of discipline and technical issues were the main challenges that students and teachers faced during the lessons. However, some students noticed that they actually improved some of their skills, such as working with a stylus or a meeting app. Additionally, some students noticed that their punctuality improved, which cannot be said about discipline during the lesson. Additional features such as online notebooks, group discussions and screen sharing were suggested by students and teachers in order to make this platform much better for learning purposes. We concluded that after implementing the strategies mentioned by the students and teachers this format of learning can become more effective than traditional format. However, it will take some time to take this format to its desired level.

Key words: Virtual Classroom, Traditional Classroom, discipline, technical, challenges, improvements, features, online education.

Introduction

Background:

The advancements in technology change the way of getting education. Educational institutions are now changing the lesson formats from traditional physical classes to e-learning i.e. virtual classrooms. In 2019 during the Covid-19 period, educational institutions saw the necessity of virtual classrooms. The adaptation of virtual classrooms was not easy both for teachers and students.

They faced different types of challenges in this process of adaptation. The complexity of learning in virtual classrooms emphasizes different teaching methods, as well as problems with adaptation and risks of using virtual classrooms in assessment tasks. (Bower, 2006, p. 1). Bower (2006) studied that pedagogues' understanding how they could use capabilities of the media and circumvent its limitations is the significant impact on students' effective educational experience (p. 1). Another study says that teaching is a kind of art and it depends on teachers' skills and experience, and on the techniques that are used during lessons (Biswas & Nandi, 2020, p. 1). The engagement of students during the lessons is also an important matter when it comes to the adaptation of any format of learning. According to the study of two researchers, since the students were free from social limitations in Virtual classes, some uninvolved students in a regular classroom could demonstrate high engagement and productivity in Virtual classes (Powers & Mitchell, 1997, p. 5).

The one question that arises is whether virtual classrooms are as effective as traditional classrooms and how students and teachers think about it. A lot of research papers are available in this regard but most of them have different limitations as this topic is wide so the result of the research varies from place to place, student to student, and teacher to teacher.

One of the best ways to find this out is to ask students and teachers who already have experience with virtual classrooms. This is done by taking surveys and interviews of both of them. And then analyzing their feedback. The students & teachers of Astana IT University participate in these surveys and interviews.

This research paper stresses the adaption of this format of learning by teachers & students, the positives and negatives of this system of learning as well as relevant platforms and recommendations for the improvements of this format.

Educational institutions and policymakers can get insights into current trends and different experiences of virtual classrooms. Students and teachers can also highlight their weaknesses and how to overcome them to use virtual classrooms most effectively.

Problem Statement:

It is necessary to find out whether virtual classrooms are as good as traditional classrooms when it comes to academic performance and teaching quality.

Research Objectives:

The objective of research is to examine the effects of Virtual classrooms on students and teachers which includes accessibility, academic integrity and its adaptation.

We will also focus on the strategies which we can implement to have a better long lasting distance learning system.

Also, to study the impact of virtual classrooms by getting feedback from students and teachers.

Research Questions:

What are the potential drawbacks and positives of virtual classrooms for teachers?

What are the effects of virtual classrooms on students' academic performances and their discipline?

What are the measurements that can be taken to improve the effectiveness of this format of learning?

Significance:

This study explores the effectiveness of virtual classrooms, offering insights for educators and policymakers. By analyzing teachers and students' feedback, we identified strengths and weaknesses of Virtual Classrooms. These findings will help improve Virtual Classroom and

online education strategies, increasing its adaptability and effectiveness to meet diverse educational needs.

Definitions

Key Terms:

For Biswas and Nandi (2020), virtual classroom means that it's a teaching-learning tool set that intends to increase students' learning experience with the help of technological devices or gadgets. (p. 334). Also, it's an online learning environment which may be web-based and accessed through a portal or software-base and require a downloadable executable file (Rouse, as cited in Biswas & Nandi, 2020). According to Ferriman (2013, as cited in Biswas & Nandi, 2020), it even allows students to communicate with each other and view their presentations.

Andersson (2002) uses the term “Virtual Classroom” to refer to the fact that it's basically a “virtual place to meet”. It allows students to connect students and teachers, and provides students test, check and discuss their knowledge (p. 1).

To be honest, the first definition we like greatly more, because it defines that “it's a tool” for learning and teaching – one of the ways to share knowledge. The relation is direct with our research paper.

Methods

Surveys:

Since we conducted research on teachers and students, our research survey was divided into two separate surveys. But, despite being separate, their structure was almost the same. Surveys itself were conducted on Google Forms platform.

The first thing that respondents encounter when they open our survey is the "Consent Form", which consists of a brief introduction, benefits, risks, data confidentiality and terms of consent. After that, there is a specific question where the respondent chooses whether he agrees to take the survey or not. Further, the survey structure does not differ in any way from the surveys we are already familiar with and consists, for the most part, of closed-end questions and at least 3 open-end questions. Our main goal was to find out how effective and how strong the impact of Virtual Classrooms is on teachers and students, so our questions were aimed specifically at such aspects as: satisfaction, complexity, adaptability, accessibility, etc. of teachers and students. There were also such direct questions, such as: "Which type of education is more comfortable for you?".

Focus Group Interviews:

The focus group interviews were conducted on the Microsoft Teams platform. Before the interview began, we talked about our topic, goals, and questions that would be asked during the interview so that our interviewees would be ready to give a clear answer. During the interview itself, we briefly talked about Virtual Classrooms in general, then asking the main questions, but we also asked additional questions to better understand the answers of our respondents. There were 3 main questions, one of which was taken from our survey, as we considered it the most significant. We justified the choice of this topic by the desire to find out how teachers and students relate to this type of education, and what improvements need to be made so that it does not yield to the traditional one.

Participants:

We did not have a strict selection of participants, since we conducted research at the university. But we had a condition that our respondents answered the survey questions adequately, because the results of our analysis would depend on it.

Teachers and students of the University of Astana took part in our survey and interview. There were 22 respondents in total, 8 of whom were teachers. Also, 3 students took part in the interview.

Data Collection Procedures:

A mandatory requirement in research surveys is the Consent Form, which ensures the ethical conduct of research. This part is very important, as it carries several functions at once, such as: information and ethical support. Through the Consent Form, we show respondents that we respect their rights, comply with ethical and legal requirements, and ensure confidentiality. We also want to note that we conducted the survey almost entirely in 3 languages (English, Russian and Kazakh), which may allow more participants to conveniently complete our survey, as well as reduce ethical barriers.

Data Analysis:

The analysis of quantitative issues was based on the presented diagrams, histograms, etc. and was carried out quite smoothly. On the other hand, we analyzed qualitative questions by examining the interview responses and open-ended survey questions. To analyze qualitative questions, we first divided the interviewees' answers into 'codes,' which were subtopics. Then, by comparing the general topics or ideas of the codes and the respondents' answers to open questions, we created three main 'themes' that reflected the results of these qualitative questions

Results

Survey Results:

The survey was conducted among teachers and students at a university in Astana. The main issue which was faced by students and teachers both is the discipline violation, almost three-quarters of teachers and eighty five percent of students noticed the discipline violation. Approximately 40%

teachers and more than half students faced technical problems during virtual lessons. Exactly half of teachers believe that online learning has a negative impact on student learning, and only 12% think that it has a positive impact. More than 70% of students do not believe that virtual learning can be more effective than the traditional method of teaching and for this reason one fourth of the students assimilate the educational material terribly, the rest of the students assimilate the material acceptably or well.

Focus Group Findings:

Most interviewees noted that technological difficulties, like internet connectivity, were particularly bad for their ability to study. The majority of respondents also miss the physical interaction between teacher and student as according to Participant Z: "I also miss the personal interaction with teachers and classmates". Maintaining discipline in virtual classrooms is also difficult as compared to traditional classrooms as two-fifth of our participants sometimes struggle with discipline. Approximately half of students were distracted more often by other activities going around them. Students and teachers both stressed on the improvement of technical issues like internet connectivity etc. And also they emphasized on the need of additional features such as note taking applications , discussion forums and also formation of communication groups for better interaction between teachers and students. On the positive side , students also saw some improvements, for instance they developed the skill of time management and teachers also noticed some development in their teaching strategies particularly in this format of learning.

Discussion

Interpretation of Results:

Violation of discipline is one of the main issues that both teachers and students face and the possible reason for it can be the lack of physical interaction between teacher and students. By using

reliable devices and making sure the availability of a smooth internet connection may help to overcome the technical problems. These results suggest a need for the improvement of quality and online teaching methodology.

Comparisons with Prior Research:

Most of the results of this research are actually much similar with prior studies. According to Bower (2006), the adaptation of different teaching methods can be challenging for students and teachers, which we can see in our surveys and interview's answers. On the other hand, the feedback of our teachers and students contradicts with the study of Powers and Mitchell (1997). While Powers and Mitchell (1997) suggest that some uninvolved students in a traditional classroom could demonstrate high engagement and productivity in virtual classes, most of our respondents noted a lack of engagement during virtual lessons.

Limitations:

One of the limitations of this study is the number of respondents who participated in the data collection. In our opinion, such a small number of respondents will not fully show the current situation and the future of Virtual Classrooms. In addition to the small number of respondents, this list can also include the fact that the survey and interview were conducted among teachers and students of only one university, which has a narrow field of specialties. This arrangement can lead to the fact that our results will be incomplete and will vary from one specialty to another.

Future Research:

This study gives a direction to future researchers to identify the possible solutions of technical issues such as internet connectivity by conducting interviews/surveys with the internet providers and other relevant government institutions and also identifying best practices and effective tools in order to maintain the discipline during the virtual lessons.

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Appendix

Consent Form:

You are invited to participate in a web-based online survey on approach of researchers to find out how exactly Virtual Classes actually effective. This is a research project being conducted by Zhansaya Aralkhan, Nurbolat Kairbolatov, Aidyn Marat and MahammadAli Javed, a students at Astana IT University. It should take approximately 7-10 minutes to complete.

Benefits:

After completing this survey you may open for yourself some new stuff about our research topic, that you didn't know before. Also this survey may be the reason for you to be motivated and engagement to developing in such area.

Risks:

Maybe some questions can be repellent for you for some specific reason. But if during taking a survey you start to feel uncomfortable, you are absolutely free to end this survey.

Confidentially:

Your survey answers will be sended to Google form.com where data will be stored and used after some number of participants will be achieved. This survey don't ask for your name, email and any personal information, so it's absolutely anonymous and confidential.

Consent:

After clicking on “Yes, I agree” button and submit your answers, you accept that all your answers will be used for our research topic.

Some questions were generated with using ChatGPT AI

Interview questions:

What changes do you think need to be made to the virtual format to make it more efficient?

How was your experience studying in virtual classrooms as a student?

Survey questions:

For teachers:

1. Do you notice any changes in discipline and student engagement in the virtual classroom compared to face-to-face learning?
2. Evaluate the level of student and teachers' satisfaction with the quality of virtual lessons on a scale from 1 to 10
3. How do you assess the impact of the virtual learning format on the academic performance of students?
4. What difficulties do you experience in organizing the learning process and interacting with students in a virtual environment?
5. Do you think that virtual learning can be more effective than the traditional format in some cases? If so, which ones exactly?
6. Which type of education is more comfortable for you, and more effective for students?

7. What new competencies and skills did you have to develop to work effectively in the virtual classroom?
8. What changes do you think need to be made to the virtual format to make it more efficient?
9. How often do you encounter technical problems during virtual lessons?
10. Evaluate the effectiveness of student feedback in a virtual environment on a scale from 1 to 10
11. How often do students break discipline during virtual lessons compared to traditional lessons?
12. What aspects and advantages of virtual lectures do you consider the most influential for student learning, compared to traditional lectures?
13. How much does the time to prepare for a lesson in a virtual format differ compared to the traditional one?
14. How often do you feel tired and distracted by other activities during virtual lessons compared to traditional classes?
15. Evaluate your level of motivation to provide material to students in virtual lessons compared to traditional classes from 1 to 10

For Students:

1. Do you notice any changes in discipline and student engagement in the virtual classroom compared to face-to-face learning?
2. Evaluate the level of student and teachers' satisfaction with the quality of virtual lessons on a scale from 1 to 10

3. How do you assess the impact of the virtual learning format on the academic performance of students?
4. Do you think that virtual learning can be more effective than the traditional format in some cases? If so, which ones exactly?
5. What new competencies and skills did you have to develop to work effectively in the virtual classroom?
6. What changes do you think need to be made to the virtual format to make it more efficient?
7. How often do you encounter technical problems during virtual lessons?
8. How often do students break discipline during virtual lessons compared to traditional lessons?
9. What aspects and advantages of virtual lectures do you consider the most influential in learning, compared to traditional lectures?
10. What kind of training is more effective and comfortable for you?
11. How often do you feel tired and distracted by other activities during virtual lessons compared to traditional classes?
12. How well do you assimilate the material in a virtual learning format?
13. Evaluate your level of motivation to study the material in virtual lessons compared to traditional classes from 1 to 10